

Enhancing Theta Rhythms in Dementia Rehabilitation Through Virtual Reality: A Machine Learning Approach Inspired by Hippocampal Oscillation Studies

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Providing effective health care in low-resource settings has many challenges including lack of financial resources, inadequate facilities and infrastructure, poorly educated and trained staff, absence of equipment, and political instability. The provision of adequate healthcare, especially for chronic illness like dementia, in such settings becomes practically impossible. Here, we propose to overcome these difficulties by designing a new low-cost, technology-assisted method for the rehabilitation of dementia.

This research focuses on the development and evaluation of a new program based on three factors: Electroencephalography, Virtual Reality and cognitive rehabilitation; with the primary objective of diagnosing and analyzing the brain rhythms - EEG signal before, during and after this rehabilitation therapy. The machine learning (ML) model developed in this work will characterize individuals showing readiness for VR interventions and the potential to improve cognitive functions so that they may improve the quality of life for both patients and caregivers. Theta rhythms are essential for memory and learning nonetheless, they are targeted to enhance the hippocampus through personalized VR experiences, provided as a non-invasive. and affordable intervention.

The research methodology involves several phases:

1. Participant Recruitment: Involves diverse participants, including those with normal cognition, MCI, and early-stage dementia.
2. Initial Assessments: Establish baseline cognitive functions using tools such as MMSE, MoCA, and ADAS-Cog.
3. VR Environment Development: Create engaging and therapeutic VR environments tailored to individual cognitive needs.
4. Session Structure: Implement a structured and adaptive VR therapy regimen, integrating EEG monitoring.
5. EEG Data Collection: Capture comprehensive EEG data to analyze neural responses and track changes over time.
6. Machine Learning Integration: Develop and train ML models to predict cognitive improvement potential based on EEG and cognitive assessment data.
7. Deployment and Validation: Ensure the predictive module's accuracy through real-world application and feedback.

This research is particularly significant for low-resource settings where traditional dementia care options are limited. By leveraging advancements in neuroscience and technology, it provides an innovative solution that is both scalable and sustainable. The VR-based rehabilitation program is designed to be adaptable, making it suitable for diverse healthcare environments, including those with limited resources.

Such research is especially important in the context of low-resource settings, where traditional options for dementia care are often limited. It gives innovatory, scalable and sustainable solution by utilizing the advances in Neuroscience and technology. It has been designed as an adaptable rehabilitation program that can be used across diverse healthcare environments including limited resources.

Keywords: Dementia Rehabilitation, Cognitive Rehabilitation, Virtual Reality (VR), EEG Theta Rhythms, Machine Learning (ML), EEG Data Analysis